

MORTALITY RATE PREDICTION USING K-NEAREST NEIGHBOUR

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This seminar paper's goal is to investigate how K-Nearest neighbour can be used to forecast death rates. We will start by giving a general overview of the major variables that affect mortality rates and how they relate to mortality rates.

The results of this study can help policymakers build successful public health programmers that aim to lower mortality rates. They can also give valuable new insights into the factors that affect mortality rates. Additionally, the planning of healthcare and resource allocation may be significantly impacted by the use of linear regression in mortality rate prediction.

II. K-NEAREST NEIGHBOUR

The supervised machine learning algorithm K-nearest neighbour (KNN) is used for classification or regression applications. According to the majority class of its k-nearest neighbour in the training set, a new data point is categorized using KNN.

To begin, the method trains on a dataset of labeled instances, where each example is a vector of features with a corresponding class label. The algorithm goes through the training data to identify the k nearest neighbour to a new input data point when one is provided. Euclidean distance is typically employed to measure the distance between data points, however other distance metrics, such as Manhattan distance, can also be utilized.

The technique guesses the class of the new data point by obtaining a majority vote of the class labels of its k-nearest neighbour after identifying the k-nearest neighbour. If the classes are tied, the algorithm can break the tie by applying a straightforward rule, such as selecting the class of the closest neighbour.

KNN is a straightforward and understandable algorithm, but the choice of distance measure and the value of k can have a significant impact on how well it performs. Although larger values of k result in smoother decision boundaries, they can also have a negative impact on how well a model performs on noisy or sparse datasets. Due to the fact that the distance between data points tends to grow as the number of

The use of measurable models to estimate passing rates has picked-up ubiquity in recent years. For displaying the interface between a subordinate variable (in this case, mortality rate) and one or more free components (such as age, sexual orientation, financial status, etc.), one such demonstration is direct relapse, which could be a broadly used method within the field of the study of disease transmission. The most important drivers of mortality rates can be recognized using direct relapse, and future mortality rates can be anticipated based on changes in these drivers.

dimensions rises, KNN is likewise plagued by the problem of dimensionality

KNN is a prominent method used in applications including image recognition, text classification, and recommended systems. It may be used for both classification and regression problems. It is frequently employed as a component of an ensemble approach, such as the random forest algorithm, together with other algorithms.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

R Anandhan, et al. [1], proposes Covid 19 outbreak data analysis and prediction they analysis morality rate of different states in India and predicted and analyses morality using linear regression.

F. Kavaklioglu et al. [2] proposes the method of Prediction of in-hospital mortality using logistic regression and machine learning techniques. This paper compares the performance of logistic regression and machine learning techniques in predicting in-hospital mortality rates in critically ill patients.

S Sulthana et al.[3] proposes the method of linear regression model for predicting mortality of cancer patients in palliative care. This paper develops a linear regression model to predict mortality rates of cancer patients receiving palliative care.

X. Yang et al.[5] proposes the method of Prediction of Mortality Risk for Critically Ill Patients with Sepsis Using Random Forest Model.

S. Samarakoon et al.[6] proposes the method of Predicting In-Hospital Mortality in Acute Myocardial Infarction Patients Using Random Forest and Logistic Regression Models

M. T. Islam et al.[4] proposes a machine learning approach for Mortality Prediction of COVID-19 Patients

S. Raj et al.[7] proposes a method of Predicting Patient Mortality in Intensive Care Units Using Gradient Boosting Machines

D. Meireles et al. [4] Prediction of cardiovascular mortality in hemodialysis patients using linear and non-linear regression models

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

We are implementing a system that analyze and predict morality rate caused by a particular diseases in a taluk using previous years morality rate of different diseases. This system may be useful for reducing morality rate on the coming years and they can which diseases have high mortality and chance of causing next years mortality rate. We only include 4 factors in the data set they are year, total population average age and percentage of death. We can easily analyze which disease is more affected to the people. We are predicting morality rate using K-Nearest Neighbour

Basic regression analysis is performed on the dataset where we determine the relations amidst a dependent variable and one or more independent variables depend on the given aspects .

We are predicting morality using linear regression method. We only use two data month and death rate per 100000.

V. RESULT

We are predicting morality rate of each month using linear regression method.

Figure 1: The output screenshot

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

Predicting mortality rates has grown in significance in healthcare, especially in light of the prevalence of chronic diseases and the ageing population. Here are some potential directions for mortality rate prediction in the future, including increased precision, early detection, etc. Predicting death rates has a lot of potential for enhancing patient outcomes and guiding public health initiatives. We may anticipate continuing development in this area and more complex mortality rate prediction models as additional data sources and machine learning techniques become accessible.

VII. CONCLUSION

It may be inferred from the study and findings presented in this seminar report that linear regression can be an effective method for forecasting morality rates. We are predicting morality rate of future year using previous year data set. We can easily identify which month have low and high accuracy rate. To create more precise models and comprehend the intricate links between numerous causes and mortality rates, additional study and analysis may be required.

VIII. REFERENCES

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